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2 **Figure S1.** Generalized linear model (GLM) adjustment for variables dominant frequency
 3 (DF) (up) and chirp rate (Ch/s) (bottom).

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5 **Figure S2.** Generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) adjustment for chirp duration (Ch/d)
 6 (up), interval between chirps (I/Ch) (center) and chirp period (Ch/p) (bottom).